

Correlation between Systemic Biomarkers and Retinal Vein Occlusion: A Case Controlled Study

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 26-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Retinal Vein occlusion (RVO) is the second most prevalent retinal vascular condition, occurring after diabetic retinopathy. It leads to painless vision impairment. RVO can be caused by a combination of several systemic, local, and hematologic illnesses. Recent studies have shown that certain inflammatory biomarkers and hyperlipidemia are more commonly linked to RVO. The objective of our investigation is to establish the correlation between systemic biomarkers and RVO. This correlation can assist patients with retinal vein occlusion (RVO) in recognizing other systemic diseases and in averting the occurrence of RVO in their other eyes.

Material and Methods: In this retrospective study, a total of 50 patients were recruited from the Department of Ophthalmology, S.S. Medical College and affiliated Gandhi Memorial Hospital, Rewa (M.P.). The investigation was conducted after obtaining approval from the institutional ethics committee and obtaining informed written consent from the patients. Data collection involved obtaining a thorough medical history. Additionally, all participants in the research underwent a full eye examination. Laboratory tests were conducted to measure levels of inflammatory markers (CRP, Homocysteine) and lipid profile parameters (Cholesterol, Triglyceride, VLDL, LDL, HDL levels, MHR). The statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 24. The data was reported using the mean and standard deviation, or proportions when applicable.

Results: The demographic characteristics of the two groups were similar. The average CRP and Homocysteine levels were considerably elevated in the patients compared to the controls. The lipid profile parameters, with the exception of HDL, exhibited considerable increases in individuals with RVOs.

Conclusion: The present study demonstrates a correlation between retinal vein occlusion (RVO) and the inflammatory markers C-reactive protein (CRP) and homocysteine. These indicators might be considered as risk factors in the development of RVO. The present investigation has determined that it is necessary to assess the blood cholesterol levels of all patients who have experienced retinal vascular obstruction. It is uncertain if restoring normal levels of lipids in the blood may improve vision and prevent the occurrence of retinal vein occlusion (RVO) in the other eye, or if it can reduce complications and the recurrence of RVO in the same eye.

Keywords: CRP; Homocysteine; Inflammatory markers; Lipid profile; Retinal Vein occlusion.

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Introduction

The second most prevalent retinal vascular disease, after diabetic retinopathy, which results in painless vision impairment, is retinal vein occlusion (RVO). The multifactorial aetiology of RVO can be attributed to a number of systemic, local, and hematologic illnesses. Hypertension, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, atherosclerosis, obesity, smoking, trauma, glaucoma, thrombophilia, hyper

viscosity, coagulation disorders, hyper-homocysteinemia, use of oral contraceptives, and ageing are diseases that may raise the risk of developing RVO. [1, 2] Many illnesses are thought to be developed as a result of endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress, and inflammation brought on by monocytes. It is commonly recognised that HDL cholesterol has anti-

inflammatory and antioxidant qualities. When there is inflammation, the liver generates C-reactive protein (CRP), and those with RVO have higher CRP levels. [3] Elevated homocysteine is a separate risk factor for retinal vascular occlusive disease. [4-6] RVO may also occur more commonly in individuals with hyperlipidemia, according to recent studies. Numerous systemic markers are associated with the pathophysiology of RVO. Despite this, their relationship is still in its early stages. Our research attempts to ascertain the correlation among homocysteine, lipid profile, and CRP in RVO patients. Patients with RVO may be able to prevent the development of RVO in other eyes by using this relationship to identify other systemic disorders.

Aim and Objectives:

The objective of this study is to establish the correlation between systemic biomarkers and RVO.

Material and Methods:

This study is an observational case-control study conducted on 50 patients who were diagnosed with various forms of retinal vein occlusion. The study took place at the Retina Clinic of the Department of Ophthalmology, S.S. Medical College, and attached Gandhi Memorial Hospital in Rewa, Madhya Pradesh, from January 2021 to September 2022. The research was approved by the Ethical Committee and obtained complete informed written permission from the patients.

Inclusion criteria: Recently diagnosed with retinal vein occlusion (RVO) in a minimum one eye

Exclusion criteria:

- The patient is now using a hypolipidemic medicine, undergoing anticoagulant therapy, utilising a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug, and using oral contraceptives.
- The patient has a comorbidity of another connective tissue disease.
- The patient is experiencing both acute and chronic disease, which is causing abnormalities in systemic indicators.
- Patient diagnosed with malignancies

Data collection and method:

The collected data encompassed demographic factors such as age and gender, as well as comprehensive information on medication usage, including hypolipidemic drugs, anticoagulants, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, and oral contraceptives.

Additionally, the data included details on systemic conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, and cerebrovascular accidents, as well as any addiction to tobacco or cigarette smoking.

An extensive ocular examination was conducted on all participants in the trial, encompassing assessments of visual acuity, intraocular pressure, anterior segment examination, and dilated ophthalmoscopy. Perform a comprehensive blood analysis including a complete blood count, serum lipid profile, C reactive protein (CRP), and serum Homocysteine simultaneously.

Figure 1: Fundus photograph: Control

Figure 2: Central Retinal Vein Occlusion (CRVO)

Figure 3: Branch Retinal Vein Occlusion (BRVO)

Figure 4: Hemi-Retinal Vein Occlusion (HRVO)

Sample size calculation:

The sample size for the proposed study is approximately 90.

N (total population in orthopedic deterrent for our current study) = 316 (near about)

N (sample size for current study) = 90

Z = Statistics for level of confidence (i.e. 1.96 for 95% confidence level) or Alpha error

Confidence level is 95% and 5% confidence interval.

P = expected prevalence of proximal tibia fractures using CT SCAN based on classification = 9% = 0.09

e = Margin of error = 5% = 0.05 (Allowable error)

$$n = \left[\frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{e^2} \right] / \left[1 + \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{Ne^2} \right]$$

$$n = \frac{[(1.96)^2 (0.09)(1-0.09)] / (0.05)^2}{1 + \frac{[(1.96)^2 (0.09)(1-0.09)]}{316 (0.05)^2}}$$

= 90.022 $\approx$ 90 (This is the required sample size)

Statistical Analysis:

The data will be collected randomly and tabulated, and then analyzed using the proper statistical software "SPSS Vs 21". The data will be provided in the form of the mean, accompanied by the

standard deviation or proportions, depending on the context. The mean, median, standard deviation, and variance will be computed, and the subsequent statistical significance tests will be conducted.

1. Categorical values were compared using the "Chi-square Test" for statistical analysis.
2. The statistical study involved the use of the "Gaussian Test/Single mean test" to compare continuous data, namely age.

3. "Post hoc test" or "multiple comparison test." The Post Hoc Test is a crucial component of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

4. An unpaired t-test is also utilized to compare the means of two continuous data sets. A "p-value" is deemed non-significant when it exceeds 0.05, and significant when it is less than 0.05.

Results:

The study population's demographic profile is displayed in [Table 1]. Regarding the distribution of age and gender, there were statistically insignificant variations between the two groups ($p=0.0972$ and $p=0.6875$). The mean CRP and homocysteine level (micromole/L) between the two groups showed statistically significant differences amongst the patients, with $p < 0.0001$.

Table 1: Demographic variables

Variables		Case (n=50)		Control (n=50)		P-value
Age group (years) (Mean±SD)		57.14±10.55		60.10±6.70		0.0972 (NS)
Gender		Male	32	Male	24	0.6875 (NS)
		Female	18	Female	26	
Distribution of Inflammatory markers	CRP	CRVO	12.09 ± 7.38	6.07±5.48		<0.0001 (S)
		BRVO	13.35 ± 11.13			
		HRVO	25.72 ± 9.15			
	Homocysteine	CRVO	23.19 ± 10.94	10.45±4.46		<0.0001 (S)
		BRVO	27.01 ± 14.52			
		HRVO	33.26 ± 14.68			

NS- Not Significant, S- Significant

With a p value of less than 0.0001, the mean values of cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, VLDL, cholesterol/HDL, LDL/HDL, and triglyceride/HDL were statistically significantly higher in the case group compared to the control group. Moreover, there was a statistically significant difference in mean HDL between the two groups (p<0.0001) between the cases and controls. [Table 2]

Table 2: Distribution of Lipid Profile among groups

Clinical features	CRVO (n=29)	BRVO (n=16)	HRVO (n=5)	Control (n=50)	P-value
Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	207.99±48.62	202.14±36.73	199.69±39.67	173.88±17.15	<0.0001(S)
TG (mg/dl)	176.14±53.94	175.10±55.62	199.15±106.46	114.71±27.51	<0.0001(S)
HDL (mg/dl)	47.95±7.74	44.06±9.89	48.46±10.73	61.59±5.57	<0.0001(S)
LDL (mg/dl)	107.78±38.83	111.72±33.14	108.71±43.60	78.02±15.48	<0.0001(S)
VLDL (mg/dl)	36.18±8.52	35.36±8.84	40.69±8.39	22.25±7.61	<0.0001(S)
Cholesterol/HDL ratio	4.46±1.30	4.79±1.26	4.43±1.80	2.85±0.39	<0.0001(S)
LDL/HDL	2.33±0.98	2.70±1.07	2.46±1.49	1.28±0.31	<0.0001(S)
TG/HDL	3.83±1.48	4.23±1.66	4.62±3.50	1.88±0.47	<0.0001(S)
MHR (monocyte to HDL ratio)	0.009±0.003	0.011±0.004	0.011±0.008	0.009±0.002	0.3077 (NS)

NS- Not Significant, S- Significant

Graph 1: Distribution of Lipid Profile among Case and Control groups

Graph 2: Distribution of Lipid Profile among CRVO, BRVO, HRVO and Control groups

Discussion:

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the various functions of inflammatory indicators and their correlation as risk factors in the development of RVO. The most widely recognised explanation for RVO, despite the lack of a conclusive explanation, is Virchow's triad, which includes venous stasis, endothelial dysfunction, and hypercoagulability.

Statistically substantially ($p < 0.0001$), the mean CRP value of the patients was greater than that of the controls. Additionally, it was observed that the mean CRP of HRVO patients was considerably greater than the mean CRP of BRVO and CRVO patients. This suggests that an increased CRP is associated with an increased risk of developing HRVO.

According to the findings of Dodson PM et al. [3], individuals with high blood pressure and elevated serum CRP levels may be at a higher risk of developing retinal vascular occlusion. According to research by Lee HH et al. [7] and Karagoz IK et al. [8], elevated hs-CRP levels may potentially be a risk indicator for the development of RVO.

The average levels of homocysteine among the patients in the current investigation were statistically substantially higher ($p < 0.0001$). The mean homocysteine value of HRVO patients was also discovered to be greater than that of CRVO and BRVO cases, indicating a higher prevalence of

elevated homocysteine in HRVO cases relative to CRVO and BRVO cases. According to Abu El-Asrar AM et al. [9], Koylu MT et al. [10], and Lahiri KD et al. [11], plasma total homocysteine levels were considerably greater among patients having retinal vascular occlusive disease than in healthy controls.

While the levels of homocysteine in the RVO group were more elevated than those in the control group, McGimpsey SJ et al. [12] and Boyd S et al. [13] showed that the difference had not been statistically significant. With a p value of less than 0.0001, the mean values of cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, VLDL, cholesterol/HDL, LDL/HDL, and triglyceride/HDL were statistically significantly higher in the case group compared to the control group. Moreover, there was a statistically significant difference in mean HDL between the two groups ($p < 0.0001$) between the patients and controls.

In a research comparing adult RVO with blood lipid levels, Agrawal S et al. [14] found that patients in the RVO group had significantly higher levels of total cholesterol and triglycerides than the control group. When compared to the controls, the RVO group's HDL levels were significantly lower.

Consistent with our findings, Lahiri KD et al. [11] and Dodson PM et al. [3] also discovered that patients with RVO had significantly lower levels of HDL cholesterol ($P < 0.001$) and significantly higher

levels of total cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL cholesterol, and VLDL cholesterol ($P < 0.001$) than control subjects. RVO patients showed greater levels of triglycerides, LDL-C, and total cholesterol, according to Lecumberri JJ et al. [15]; however, these changes were not statistically significant.

The case and control groups in a research by Buehl W et al. [16] differed significantly, according to a retrospective analysis. There was just one metric on which there was a significant difference between the RVO patient population and the control group, and that was HDL phospholipid levels. Although these changes were not statistically significant, the patient group had greater concentrations of lipids and apolipoproteins connected to VLDL and lower quantities of numerous lipids and apolipoproteins linked to LDL. They concluded that there may be a connection between HDL phospholipids and the development of retinal vascular obstruction.

Limitations of the study:

The current study's results may have been impacted by the variation in the cases' evaluation times from the point of beginning. The results cannot be extrapolated to the entire population due to the limited sample size. Another potential source of bias was the way blood samples were obtained for the current trial, which was contingent on patient visits to the ophthalmology unit. Consequently, patients who were fasting had their blood not taken, which might have had a significant effect on the values of the lipid profile.

All of the indicators that were noticeably higher in HRVO cases were explained by the minimal number of cases seen in the case group. Consequently, in order to analyze the conclusion further, a larger sample size is needed.

Conclusion

The current study shows a relationship between RVO and the inflammatory markers homocysteine and CRP, which may be regarded as risk factors for the onset of RVO. The current study found that blood cholesterol levels should be monitored in all patients with retinal vascular obstruction. It is not yet known, however, if returning serum lipid levels to normal can improve vision and prevent RVO in the affected eye, or if it will only minimize issues and the likelihood of RVO recurring in the same eye.

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